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Antixenotic and Allelochemicals Study on Snapmelon (*Cucumis melo* var. *momordica*) against Melon Fruit Fly (*Bactrocera Cucurbitae* (Coquillett)) in Arid Region Rajasthan, India

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Background: Snapmelon (*Cucumis melo* L. var. *momordica* (Roxb.) belongs to family *Cucurbitaceae* that is a native of India and is used as vegetable in a variety of ways. Tephritid fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) are devastating insect pests having a foremost influence on global agricultural products affecting yield losses, and dropping the value and marketability of snapmelon crops. The extent of losses varies between 30 and 100%, depending on the cucurbit species and the season.

Methods: Fourty three genotypes of snapmelon were sown at experimental farm of ICAR-Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Bikaner (28°06'N, 73°21'E). Two pickings were done during the entire growing season of snapmelon. Ten fruits were randomly selected from each picking from each experimental bed (replication) of each genotype and were brought to the laboratory for microscopic examination for fruit fly infestation.

Results & Conclusions: The per cent fruit infestation was highest in IC-430184 (69.67 %) and lowest in IC-430190 (11.21 %) followed by DKS-AHS-2011/4 (14.97 %). The percentage fruit infestation and the larval density per fruit with free amino acid and TSS of fruit had a significant positive correlation whereas; flavonoid, tannins, phenols and total alkaloid had significant negative correlation. The length of ovary pubescence, rind hardness at immature stage, rind hardness at mature stage and pericarp thickness had significant negative correlations whereas; flesh thickness, fruit length and fruit diameter had significant positive correlations with the percentage fruit infestation and the larval density per fruit. Basis on Kaiser Normalization method, the extraction communalities for all the variables tested were ≥ 0.5 indicating that the variables were well represented by the extracted PCs which together explained a cumulative variation of 82.8 %. PC1 explained 53.41 % of the variation while PC2 explained 29.39 % of variation. The flavonoid, total alkaloid, tannins, phenols content, length of ovary pubescence and rind hardness were the novel antibiosis and antixenotic characters found in snapmelon which were resistant to fruit fly. Snapmelon genotypes IC-430190, DKS-AHS 2011/4, DKS-AHS 2011/3 and IC-430176 were classified as resistant to *B. cucurbitae* and these could be used in future breeding programme as resistant sources.

Keywords: *Cucumis melo* var. *momordica*, *Bactrocera cucurbitae*, Antixenotic, Allelochemicals